

Metal Complexes of 3,4-Dimethoxybenzaldehyde Thiosemicarbazone†

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The reaction of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} salts with 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (LH) in mixed alcohol-water or absolute alcohol yielded complexes of different stoichiometries. Their elemental analyses conductance, magnetic and electronic, ir and ^1H nmr spectral data revealed that the ligand coordinates with the metal ion either as anionic bidentate one (thiolate anion L^-) coordinating through the azomethine nitrogen and thioenol sulphur atoms or as neutral bidentate one (LH) coordinating through the azomethine nitrogen and thioketo sulphur atoms. The present ligand reduces Cu^{II} salts to Cu^{I} which forms complex.

MARKED differences have been noted in the donor properties and biological activities of thiosemicarbazones of benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes. The donor properties of thiosemicarbazones of monosubstituted benzaldehydes have been investigated in detail. Comparatively less work has been done on the complexes of thiosemicarbazones of disubstituted benzaldehydes¹. Dimethoxybenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazones and related compounds have long been studied for their biological activities². As there is no report on their metal complexes and following our interest on metal complexes with sulphur ligands^{1,3-5} we investigated the donor properties of 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone, LH towards Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} .

Experimental

All chemicals used were AnalaR grade. The solvents used were purified by standard methods. Spectroscopic grade solvents (B.D.H.) were used for spectral and conductivity measurements.

The ligand was synthesised by refluxing recrystallised 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde and thiosemicarbazide (1 : 1 ratio) in absolute alcohol for 2 h and recrystallising the product from ethanol, m.p. 206°.

Synthesis of complexes: The Co, Ni and Cu complexes were prepared by adding slowly a hot aqueous solution of the metal acetate to a refluxing

ethanolic solution of the ligand containing sodium acetate (1.50 g) until the metal to ligand ratio reached 1 : 2. The resulting solid complexes were washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over P_4O_{10} . The halogeno complexes of Co and Cu were prepared by adding absolute ethanolic solution of the metal halide (10 mmol) to refluxing absolute ethanolic solution (20 mmol) of the ligand. However, in the case of the halogeno complexes of Zn, Cd and Hg a 1 : 1 molar mixture of the respective metal halide and the ligand in absolute alcohol were used. The reaction mixture was maintained at refluxing temperature for 1 h. The solid complexes that separated on cooling the reaction mixture to room temperature were washed with ethanol and dried as before. It was observed that even though the copper complexes were of 1 : 1 type, a reaction mixture containing metal and ligand in 1 : 1 ratio resulted in poor yield of the complexes. However, from a reaction mixture containing metal and ligand in 1 : 2 ratio, an appreciable yield of the complex was noted.

The metal, sulphur and halogen present in the complexes were estimated by standard procedures⁶ and nitrogen was determined microanalytically. The molar conductance was measured using $\sim 10^{-3}$ M solutions in methanol, acetonitrile and nitrobenzene on a Biochem M-70 conductivity bridge at room temperature. Magnetic susceptibility was determined by Gouy method at room temperature. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Hitachi-220 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr disc) on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra (DMSO-d_6) on a Varian-EM 390 (90 MHz) spectrometer.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of elemental analyses and molar conductance data stoichiometry of the complexes

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TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Molar conductance $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at $10^{-3} M$ in		
	Metal	N	S	Halogen	Methanol	Acetonitrile	Nitrobenzene
[CoL ₂]	11.00 (11.02)	15.65 (15.70)	11.51 (11.99)	—	—	16.1	—
[NiL ₂]	10.61 (10.98)	15.68 (15.71)	11.39 (11.99)	—	—	—	—
[CuL]	20.74 (21.07)	13.84 (13.93)	10.34 (10.63)	—	1.2	—	—
[Co(LH)Cl ₂]	15.90 (15.98)	11.40 (11.39)	8.42 (8.70)	19.10 (19.23)	101.5	20.1	—
[Co(LH) ₂ Br ₂]	8.32 (8.46)	12.01 (12.05)	9.62 (9.20)	22.97 (22.94)	186.5	30.4	0.9
[Co(LH) ₂ I ₂]	7.49 (7.45)	10.66 (10.62)	8.05 (8.11)	32.00 (32.09)	201.9	202.7	1.5
[Cu(LH)Cl]	18.70 (18.85)	12.27 (12.46)	9.41 (9.51)	10.39 (10.52)	38.8	44.2	1.0
[Zn(LH) ₂ Cl ₂]	10.19 (10.64)	13.25 (13.67)	11.07 (10.40)	11.40 (11.54)	46.7	8.1	2.5
[Zn(LH) ₂ Br ₂]	9.59 (9.30)	12.00 (11.94)	8.91 (9.12)	22.63 (22.73)	131.0	9.0	2.1
[Zn(LH) ₂ I ₂]	8.34 (8.20)	10.33 (10.54)	7.79 (8.04)	31.80 (31.84)	92.3	34.1	4.0
[Cd(LH)Cl ₂]	26.96 (26.62)	9.90 (9.94)	7.14 (7.50)	16.82 (16.79)	91.1	16.0	1.8
[Cd(LH)Br ₂]	20.92 (20.98)	8.42 (8.21)	6.23 (6.27)	31.20 (31.26)	57.2	16.5	0.8
[Cd(LH)I ₂]	18.30 (18.57)	6.78 (6.94)	5.30 (5.30)	41.82 (41.94)	19.3	18.0	2.2
[Hg(LH) ₂ Cl ₂]	27.68 (27.12)	11.13 (11.21)	8.14 (8.67)	9.47 (9.59)	91.4	64.2	5.7
[Hg(LH) ₂ Br ₂]	23.59 (23.92)	10.10 (10.02)	7.13 (7.65)	19.10 (19.06)	38.9	27.8	1.7
[Hg(LH) ₂ I ₂]	20.74 (21.01)	9.00 (9.01)	6.12 (6.88)	27.20 (27.22)	49.9	45.7	2.9

was established (Table 1). All the complexes are stable in air and non-hygroscopic. They are soluble in polar organic solvents but insoluble in water and nonpolar organic solvents.

Molar conductance: A comparison of the observed molar conductance values in methanol, acetonitrile and nitrobenzene (Table 1) with the data available⁷ shows that the complexes CoL₂, NiL₂ and CuL behave as non-electrolytes. According to the molar conductance values, Co(LH)Cl₂, Zn(LH)₂Br₂, Zn(LH)₂I₂, Cd(LH)Cl₂ and Hg(LH)₂Cl₂ behave as 1 : 1 electrolytes and Co(LH)₂Br₂ and Co(LH)₂I₂ as 1 : 2 electrolytes in methanol. Even though the remaining complexes show considerable dissociation in methanol, their conductance values are much lower than the expected one for a 1 : 1 electrolyte in methanol. In acetonitrile, all the complexes, except Co(LH)₂I₂ (which behaves as a 1 : 2 electrolyte), behave as non-electrolyte. However, the conductivity measurements in nitrobenzene conclusively proved the non-electrolytic behaviour of all the complexes.

Magnetic properties: The cobalt complex, CoL₂ shows a magnetic moment of 2.14 B.M. Due to spin-orbit coupling, a moment greater than spin-only value (1.73 B.M.) is expected for a square-planar Co^{II} complex⁸. The complexes Co(LH)Cl₂, Co(LH)₂Br₂ and Co(LH)₂I₂ show magnetic moments

4.35, 5.17 and 5.19 B.M. respectively, which suggest tetrahedral geometry for the chloro complex and octahedral geometry for the bromo and iodo complexes⁸. The diamagnetic behaviour of NiL₂ reveals its square-planar structure⁹. The two copper complexes, CuL and Cu(LH)Cl are found to be diamagnetic, which shows presence of the metal as Cu^I. Thus complete reduction of Cu^{II} takes place in these cases during complex formation. The observation during the synthesis of these complexes that only a reaction mixture containing metal and ligand in 1 : 2 ratio resulted in an appreciable yield of these two complexes, indicates that a part of the ligand which is in excess may reduce Cu^{II} to Cu^I and the cations thus formed complex with the remaining ligand. The oxidation products of the excess of the ligand are miscible with the solvent. This was confirmed by the synthesis of the same complexes, CuL and Cu(LH)Cl using cuprous chloride. The former was obtained by reacting ammoniacal solution of CuCl with alcoholic solution of the ligand in 1 : 1 ratio and the latter by reacting acetonitrile solution of CuCl with alcoholic solution of the ligand in 1 : 1 ratio. This type of behaviour is rather common in the case of copper complexes of heterocyclic thiones^{6,10}. However, reports on this type of reducing action of thiosemicarbazones towards Cu^{II} salts are rather scanty¹¹. As expected, all the Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are diamagnetic.

Electronic spectra: The ligand showed two absorption maxima—a sharp one of the weak intensity at 223 nm due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition and a broad one of strong intensity at 328 nm due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. All the complexes have almost the same absorption pattern as that of the ligand in the uv region. This may be due to the fact that sulphur coordination may not affect π -bonding as C=S or C-S group has more than one lone pairs. The brown colour and broad bands with shoulder of weak intensity at 1000–1100 nm of CoL_2 are characteristics of square-planar geometry^{1,4}. Co(LH)Cl_2 showed an absorption band at 718 nm, which may be attributed to the transition, ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ of tetrahedral Co^{II} complex¹. In case of the bromo and iodo complexes, the bands around 550 nm may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition of an octahedral Co^{II} complex⁹. The band at 440 nm of NiL_2 may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transition of a square-planar Ni^{II} complex^{1,4}. The two copper complexes CuL and Cu(LH)Cl and the complexes of Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} do not display any characteristic band in the visible region.

Infrared spectra: The ligand exhibited three ir bands of strong intensity at 3300, 3240 and 3120 cm^{-1} which may be due to the asymmetric $\nu_{as}(\text{NH})$ of terminal NH_2 group and symmetric $\nu_s(\text{NH})$ of NH_2 and NH groups¹. It has been reported that the first two bands are due to the terminal NH_2 group and the third one is due to the secondary NH group¹². In the metal complexes, all these bands displayed substantial blue-shift with considerably lower intensity. All these observations indicate the participation of the hydrazine nitrogen of the system $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{NH}-\text{CS}-\text{NH}_2$ in the complex formation. Moreover, the absence of a band of strong intensity at 3120 cm^{-1} in the spectra of CoL_2 , NiL_2 and CuL indicates that the hydrogen atom of the secondary NH group takes part in the formation of these complexes. The absence of any bands at 2650–2500 cm^{-1} in the ligand spectrum indicates that there is no S-H group in the free ligand in solid state^{1,4}.

The band of strong intensity at 1592 cm^{-1} with a shoulder at 1605 cm^{-1} in the ligand spectrum may be assigned to azomethine stretch^{1,4}. In all the complexes it undergoes a red-shift by 20–50 cm^{-1} , indicating the participation of azomethine-N in coordination. The band of very strong intensity at 1260 cm^{-1} in the ligand spectrum may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ ¹³. The position and other characteristics of this band are retained in all the complexes. This indicates that the oxygen atoms of the methoxy groups do not take part in coordination.

The band of medium intensity at 810 cm^{-1} with distinct shoulders at 848 and 830 cm^{-1} in the ligand spectrum may be assigned to pure $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$. In a set of complexes, CoL_2 , NiL_2 and CuL which are formed in presence of sodium acetate buffer, the shoulders at 848 and 830 cm^{-1} disappeared and a new band appeared around 660 cm^{-1} (C-S). However, the band at 810 cm^{-1} is retained in the spectra of these

complexes, but at a lower frequency region with considerable reduction in intensity. These facts are compatible with the enolisation of the $-\text{NH}-\text{C}=\text{S}$ group in the ligand to $-\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{SH}$ in the presence of metal ion and coordination of the metal ion through S after deprotonation^{1,4}. In the other set of complexes, i.e. the halogeno complexes of Cu^I , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} the band in this region splitted into two—one of medium intensity around 860 cm^{-1} and the other of strong intensity at about 800 cm^{-1} . In addition a new band of weak intensity was found around 770 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes of this set. Similar behaviour of $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ has also been reported in the spectrum of Ag(TSC)Cl , where TSC=thiosemicarbazide¹¹. All these observations indicate the coordination through the sulphur atom of $-\text{NH}-\text{C}=\text{S}$ group of the ligand (without enolisation) in this set of complexes.

The bands of weak intensity around 450 cm^{-1} in the spectra of all complexes may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$.

¹H nmr spectra: The methoxy protons in the free ligand are represented by a sharp singlet at δ 3.80. In the spectra of the complexes they were found at the same position which confirms that the oxygen atoms of the methoxy groups do not take part in coordination. The two doublets at about δ 6.38 and 7.22 in the spectra of the ligand and complexes, are due to the two phenyl protons H(5) and H(6). This can easily be understood from the vicinal coupling constant ($J \approx 8.5$ Hz). The singlet at δ 7.40 is due to the third proton H(2) of the phenyl ring. The signal for the azomethine proton is expected to appear at a low field compared to the phenyl protons. Thus the singlet at δ 7.82 due to azomethine proton in the ligand spectrum, shifted downfield at δ 8.00–8.10 in the spectra of the complexes showing its deshielding as a result of coordination through the nitrogen of the azomethine group to the metal ion¹⁴. The spectra of thiosemicarbazones are expected to exhibit two resonances for the NH_2 protons indicating hindered rotation about the C(S)-NH_2 bond due to its partial double bond character¹⁵. However, in the spectrum of the present ligand, there is only a singlet at δ 8.00 for NH_2 protons. This is not unexpected as one of these signals may be obscured by that of aromatic protons as in the case of benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone. As expected, the secondary NH proton signal is found at δ 11.22 in the spectrum of the ligand. On complex formation all the resonances of the nitrogen-bonded protons shifted to low field compared with the free ligand. Further, the disappearance of secondary NH proton signal in the spectra of NiL_2 and CuL is an evidence of its deprotonation and having taken part in the complex formation. Thus the ir and ¹H nmr spectral observations supplement each other.

The data available are insufficient to predict the geometry of the Cu^I , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes. However, in comparison with similar other complexes and by considering the coordination numbers exhibited by these metal ions in their complexes and

their preferred geometries, the following assignments can be made. The Cu^{I} complexes, CuL and Cu(LH)Cl are found to be 2- and 3-coordinate respectively, and may respectively be planar and trigonal-planar in geometry. The Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes, as they are 6-coordinate, may be octahedral. The Cd^{II} complexes may be tetrahedral as it is the most preferred geometry for 4-coordinate Cd^{II} complexes.

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References

1. K. K. ARAVINDAKSHAN and C. G. R. NAIR, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1984, **93**, 111; K. K. ARAVINDAKSHAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 241.
2. T. HARRY, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, **79**, 104942; L. DEMETRIOS, *Chem. Chron.*, 1979, **8**, 141; TAN-PUTS'AO and J. TSUNG-PIN CHANG, *Kun. Chung Hsueh Pao*, 1966, **15**, 13.
3. K. K. ARAVINDAKSHAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 592, 1052.
4. K. K. ARAVINDAKSHAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 338; K. K. ARAVINDAKSHAN and K. MURALAKSHARAN, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1989, **140**, 325; *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1989, **39**, 279; *Thermochim. Acta*, 1989, **146**, 149.
5. A. MOHANAN and K. K. ARAVINDAKSHAN, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1989, **101**, 13.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", ELBS, London, 1978.
7. W. H. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
8. B. N. FIGGS and J. LEWIS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **6**, 185.
9. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1980.
10. L. A. BATTAGLIA, A. B. CORRADI, F. A. DEVILLANOVA and G. VERANI, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1979, **4**, 264.
11. M. J. M. CAMPBELL, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1975, **15**, 279.
12. B. A. GINGRAS, R. W. HORNAL and C. H. BAYLEY, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1960, **38**, 712.
13. A. N. SUNDER RAM, Ph. D. Thesis, University of Kerala, 1977.
14. R. K. SHARMA, R. V. SING and J. P. TANDON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, **42**, 463.
15. C. BELLITTO, D. GATTEGNO, A. M. GIULIANI and M. BOSSA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1976, 758.